

The Inequality Trap: Why Sub-Saharan Africa Struggles to Escape Poverty

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Cartoon: *The poverty line in Africa*

Source: © [Talal Nayer](#), n.d.

Abstract: The issue of poverty in Africa is well-known and widely researched. Around a third of the world's poorest people live in Africa. Evidence from more recent years suggests that inequality may be an even greater challenge in Africa than in other developing regions. High levels of poverty and inequality persist in Africa despite it being one of the fastest-growing regions of the last decade. In particular, six of the world's ten fastest-growing economies between 2001 and 2010 were in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Initial inequality reduces the ability of growth to reduce poverty, and even more so if inequality rises during the growth process. Although income inequality fell by 4.3% between 1990 and 2009, Africa remains the second most unequal region globally, after Latin America and the Caribbean. Inequality not only dampens the poverty-reducing impact of growth and lowers the growth rate, but also hollows out the middle class, encourages corruption and rent-seeking, increases crime and violence, undermines social stability and precludes sustained growth. Growth trends in sub-Saharan Africa are not significantly different to those of other developing countries that have fallen into a poverty trap. The combination of endemic poverty, high inequality and low growth is a major obstacle to poverty reduction and overall socio-economic development in much of Africa. Multidimensional inequality is deeply entrenched in much of Africa and exhibits vertical and horizontal dimensions that hinder human development. The roots of inequality lie in the colonial past and have been reinforced by institutions that limited access and were established by the colonisers and maintained by generations of African leaders since then. Attention should also be paid to the diachronic dimensions of inequality, especially how inequality changes over individuals' lifetimes and its effect on intergenerational mobility. As effective democratic practices take firmer root on the continent, it can be expected that pressure for general and inclusive social redistribution will increase. Providing social protection contributes to reducing poverty and inequality in Africa. Additionally, rising income inequality contributes to increased CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, an increase in poverty has a detrimental effect on environmental pollution in sub-Saharan African countries. Over half of adults infected with HIV in Africa are female, yet poverty and social structures still prevent many women from protecting themselves. Current strategies to change HIV-related behaviours continue to fail women and girls in Africa.

Keywords: [Poverty](#), [inequality](#), [economic growth](#), [Sub-Saharan Africa](#), [Nigeria](#), [South Africa](#), [DR Congo](#)

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1. Introduction

Cartoon 2: *Some burdens are heavier than others ...*

Source: © Change.org, n.d.

The poverty challenge in [Africa](#) is well known. (Bhorat et al., 2016). Around a third of the world's poorest people live in Africa. [Inequality](#) may be a more significant challenge in Africa than in other regions of the developing world. Despite being one of the fastest growing regions in the early 2000s, high levels of poverty and inequality persist in Africa. Notably, six of the world's ten fastest-growing economies between 2001 and 2010 were in [sub-Saharan Africa](#) (SSA). The period from the 1970s to the late 1990s can generally be considered lost decades for Africa since [independence](#). It was characterised by a combination of serious governance failures, low investment in health, education and other social services, significant macroeconomic imbalances, poor infrastructure and structural trade deficits (Bhorat et al., 2016).

In contrast, the post-2000 African economic boom has been built on a combination of factors, including technological advances (particularly in mobile technology), demographic growth, urbanisation, the emergence of dynamic new African cities, improved macroeconomic policy, enhanced regional cooperation and integration, more targeted social policy and significant improvements in governance and institutional quality. However, Africa's socio-economic variables have not matched this impressive economic performance: poverty and higher levels of inequality remain features of many African economies. There are three key observations regarding the relationship between growth, poverty and inequality. Firstly, growth rates among developing countries are virtually uncorrelated with changes in inequality. Secondly, if the above relationship does not exist, there must be a strong relationship between growth and changes in poverty. Faster-growing economies reduce poverty more rapidly. Thirdly, high initial inequality reduces the poverty-reducing power of growth, especially if inequality rises during the growth process (Bhorat et al., 2016).

The growth trend in Sub-Saharan Africa is not significantly different to that of other developing countries which have fallen into a [poverty trap](#). Most of the difference in growth rates between Sub-Saharan Africa and other developing countries can be explained by two measures of [human capital](#): [secondary enrolment](#) and [infant mortality](#) (Go et al., 2007).

In contrast to the earlier period of the 1980s and early 1990s, considerable progress has been made in reducing poverty. However, compared with progress in a global sample of countries, results have been mixed. Nonetheless, while African countries lag behind [Brazil](#), [India](#), [China](#) and [Russia](#) as a whole, many of them have outperformed India. Furthermore, while income

growth is generally considered to be the main driver of poverty reduction in SSA, the role of inequality is particularly important in certain countries (Fosu, 2015).

Initial endemic poverty combined with high inequality and low growth has been a major obstacle to [poverty reduction](#) and overall socio-economic development in much of Africa. There is a growth–inequality–poverty nexus, with reduced poverty leading to more inclusive growth in the context of Sub-Saharan Africa (Thorbecke, 2013). Poverty levels have declined substantially since Africa's growth resurgence in the 1990s and this progress has been mainly driven by income growth, which is consistent with global evidence. However, inequality often played a complementary role in most countries, and in a few cases it was the main driver of changes in poverty (Thorbecke, 2013).

The benefits of the growth experienced in Africa since 2000 have not been widely shared. Poverty fell by only 8.0 % points between 1990 and 2010, falling short of the target of 28.3 % points by 2015. Although income inequality fell by 4.3 % between 1990 and 2009, Africa remains the second most unequal region in the world after Latin America and the Caribbean. Despite economic growth, many Africans continue to live in poverty and experience high levels of income and opportunity inequality. Inequality not only dampens the impact of growth on poverty reduction, lowers the growth rate, hollows out the middle class, encourages corruption and rent-seeking, increases crime and violence, and undermines social stability, but it also precludes sustained growth (Ayub, 2013).

Poverty fell by only 8.0 % between 1990 and 2010 compared to the targeted 28.3 % by 2015. Although income inequality fell by 4.3 % between 1990 and 2009, Africa remains the second most unequal region globally after [Latin America](#) and the [Caribbean](#) region (Odusola, 2017). Financial development has not had a significant effect on poverty and inequality in African countries. More efforts need to be done to improve access of poor households and small and medium enterprises to financial services (Fowowe & Abidoye 2013).

Graph 1: The Human Costs of Inequality

Source: © Nel, 2018

Multidimensional inequality is deeply entrenched in much of Africa and exhibits vertical and horizontal dimensions that hinder human development (Nel, 2018). The roots of inequality lie in the [colonial past](#) and have been reinforced by institutions that restrict access and which were established by the colonisers and have been maintained by generations of African

leaders since then. There is good reason to doubt the effectiveness of extensive poverty reduction programmes as long as inequality is not addressed as a co-determinant of poor human development (Nel, 2018). Additionally, the [diachronic](#) dimensions of inequality must be analysed, particularly how inequality changes over the lifetime of individuals and its effect on intergenerational mobility (Nel, 2018). In general, Africa lacks the revenue-generating capacity to sustain systematic programmes of social assistance, social insurance and labour-market interventions. Too much capital still leaves Africa illegally. As effective democratic practices take firmer root on the continent, it can also be expected that pressure for general and inclusive social redistribution will increase. For the time being, however, these inclusive pressures have to compete with the selective in-group redistribution typical of [patron–client](#) relations, which characterise African state policies (Nel, 2018). ...

Furthermore, there exists a population–poverty–inequality nexus and social protection in Africa (Osabohien et al. (2020). A 1% increase in the provision of social protection will decrease poverty and inequality by 58% and 26%, respectively. The provision of social protection may contribute to poverty and inequality reduction in Africa. Although social protection appears to be an essential strategy for reducing, to a more considerable extent, poverty and, to a relatively lesser extent, inequality in Africa, there are also regional variations (Osabohien et al. (2020).

Moreover, rising income inequality contributes to increased [CO2 emissions](#). Furthermore, an increase in poverty has a detrimental effect on environmental pollution in Sub-Saharan African countries. The results have important policy implications in light of the Sustainable Development Goals ([SDGs](#)) (Baloch et al., 2020).

Cartoon 3: *The danger of carbon emissions to poor countries*

Source: © Rahma Cartoons, 28 August 2023

Last but not least, [gender inequality](#) is prevalent in SSA (Kim & Watts, 2005). Although over half of adults infected with [HIV in Africa](#) are female, poverty and social structures still prevent many women from protecting themselves. Current strategies to change HIV-risk behaviour continue to fail women and girls in Africa. Structural interventions that aim to empower women economically, socially and politically are a vital part of an effective AIDS strategy (Kim & Watts, 2005).

Standard inequality measures failed to detect distributional changes that did not reveal a clear pattern of inequality on the continent (Clementi et al., 2019). Nineteen out of twenty-four countries experienced a significant increase in [polarisation](#), particularly in the lower tail of the distribution. This distributional change substantially lowered the pro-poor impact of growth. Without this unfavourable redistribution, poverty in these countries could have decreased by an additional 5 % (Clementi et al., 2019).

2. Poverty is increasing amid Africa's growing economy

Cartoon 4: *International day for the eradication of poverty*²

Source: © [Luojie](#), *China Daily*

Despite the abundance of human and natural resources in Africa, millions of people across the continent live in abject poverty (Macaulay, 2023). The ruling classes in different African countries act as puppets for the International Monetary Fund ([IMF](#)) and the [World Bank](#), helping to extract wealth from the environment and the workforce. Most African countries suffer from a lack of basic infrastructure, lack of access to food, clean water and energy and mass levels of poverty. Despite borrowing massive amounts of money for infrastructure and social programs, the money is often squandered by political officeholders and embezzled through dubious contracts. [Corruption](#) is a major factor present across Africa (Macaulay, 2023).

Cartoon 5: *drivers of poverty in Africa*

Source: © Polyp.org.uk; Macaulay, 2023

² “The Grim Reaper is in the foreground, walking along and reading a newspaper whose story is entitled ‘International Day for the Eradication of Poverty’. This is a ‘annual celebration’ that is ‘designated..to promote awareness of the need to eradicate poverty and destitution in all countries.’ (Kai-moon, 2014) The irony of the situation is overpowering because as the reaper so casually ‘tips’ the personification of Africa with Ebola. He throws it in his tin can as if it is a gift, and the irony of the situation only increases when you refer back to the title of the newspaper. This day is designated to be a ‘gift’ of its own, and is being overrun by the deadly virus. Even though it is thought to the reaper to be a gift to the continent of Africa, it in no way supports the idea of the eradication of poverty, it in fact does the opposite. This is supported by the appearance of Africa in the cartoon, he is dressed like a homeless person, and begging for anything just to get by.” [Luojie](#), *China Daily*

The political crisis of capitalism in Africa has resulted in civil wars, coups, xenophobic attacks, religious crises, kidnappings, terrorism, and the rigging of elections. [Nigeria](#), the most populous country in Africa, for example, has witnessed a civil war between 1967 and 1970 and is presently grappling with loans and political crises, not to mention extreme poverty. Pre and post-election crises are commonplace and elections are often marred by violence. Many politicians have empowered their supporters to rig elections and incite violence in order to seize power and gain access to immense public wealth. The same applies to [Uganda](#). The country's debts are enormous, but the government has shown little interest in ending poverty and inequality. Despite being home to over 1 billion people, half of whom will be under 25 years old by 2050, Sub-Saharan Africa, has not been able to achieve meaningful growth for the people and eradicate poverty (Macaulay, 2023).

3. Rising inequality in a poverty-stricken Africa

Cartoon 6: *World day against child labour*

Source: © Brandan Reynolds, [Business Day](#), 12 June 2020

[Poverty reduction](#) in Africa may be slightly greater than traditional estimates suggest, although even the most optimistic estimates of poverty reduction imply that more people lived in poverty in 2012 than in 1990 (Beegle et al. ,2016). A WB study on 'Poverty in a rising Africa' reviewed the evidence on [inequality](#) in Africa. It looked not only at patterns of monetary inequality in Africa but also other dimensions, including inequality of opportunity, intergenerational mobility in occupation and education, and extreme wealth in Africa (Beegle et al. ,2016).

Inequality in Africa is a complex problem. Of the 10 most unequal countries in the world, 7 are in Africa. But African countries other than these seven do not have higher inequality than developing countries elsewhere in the world. For the region as a whole, however, inequality is high, because of the wide variation in income across countries (Beegle et al. ,2016).

An important distinction is between inequality of outcomes (such as income, consumption, and wealth) and inequality of opportunity. In the case of the latter, in many settings, circumstances over which a person has little control may largely dictate one's future. Being born poor often means being the beneficiary of less investment in human development, which determines future living standards. Inequality in outcomes, the gap between the poorest and the richest, depends not only on opportunities but also on effort and the degree to which

individuals take risks. Rewarding people for effort or risk taking can incentivize and motivate them. From this perspective, not all aspects of inequality are necessarily bad, although high levels of inequality can impose large socioeconomic cost on society (Beegle et al. ,2016).

Inequality influences how economic growth translates into poverty reduction, and it may affect growth prospects. With respect to poverty reduction, when initial inequality is higher, a larger share of poor households will have incomes farther below the poverty line, so that growth (the increase in income), will result in less poverty reduction. Tentative evidence also suggests that inequality leads to lower and less durable sustainable growth processes and thus less poverty reduction. The pathway by which inequality evolves thus matters for growth (Beegle et al. ,2016).

The heterogeneity in inequality across Africa is substantial and shows a geographical pattern. Inequality is higher in Southern Africa (Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, South Africa, Swaziland and Zambia), where Gini indexes are above 0.5, as well as in Central African Republic and the Comoros. West African countries exhibit lower levels of inequality, and countries in East Africa are mixed (Beegle et al. ,2016).

Graph 2: *Inequality in Africa shows a geographical pattern*

Source: World Bank Africa Poverty database.

Source: © Beegle et al. ,2016

Are African countries becoming more unequal? Analysis of 23 countries for which there are two comparable surveys to measure inequality reveals that about half the countries experienced a decline in inequality while the other half saw an increase. No clear patterns based on resources status, income status, or initial level of inequality in the first survey are evident (Beegle et al. ,2016).

Graph 3: *Inequality rose in about half of the countries and fell in the other half*

Source: World Bank Africa Poverty database.

Source: © Beegle et al. ,2016

Graph 4: *There is no systematic relationship between growth and inequality in Africa*

Sources: World Bank Africa Poverty database (subset of countries with comparable surveys); World Development Indicators database.

Source: © Beegle et al. ,2016

Graph 5: *Unequal opportunities account for up to 20 % of inequality in Africa*

Source: Brunori, Palmisano, and Peragine 2015b.

Note: The figure shows the share of total mean log deviation (MLD) that is attributed to inequality

Source: © Beegle et al. ,2016

4. Case Studies

Cartoon 7: social inequality in Africa

Source: © Albert Ohams, 28 April 2019

A study of trends in poverty and inequality in seven sub-Saharan African ([SSA](#)) countries ([Ghana](#), [Kenya](#), [Mali](#), [Senegal](#), [Tanzania](#), [Zambia](#) and [Zimbabwe](#)) could indicate general regional developments (Booyesen et al., 2007). Overall, poverty has declined in five of the seven countries over a period of 10 to 15 years. Trends in urban and rural poverty largely mirror these overall poverty trends. Five of the seven countries experienced an improvement in overall inequality. Only in Zambia has overall inequality increased. Overall poverty declined in five of the seven countries over this period: Ghana, Kenya, Mali, Senegal and Zimbabwe. In Zambia, however, poverty has increased during this period. Tanzania, Mali and Zambia have the highest levels of poverty, while Ghana has the lowest, followed by Kenya and Zimbabwe (Booyesen et al., 2007).

In all cases, rural poverty and inequality exceed urban poverty. Poverty is most prevalent in Tanzania, Mali and Zambia, while Ghana has the lowest level of poverty, followed by Kenya and Zimbabwe. Rural poverty and inequality exceed urban poverty in all cases. Trends in inequality are not uniform. Five out of the seven countries experienced an improvement in overall inequality during this period: Ghana, Kenya, Senegal, Tanzania and Zimbabwe. However, only Tanzania experienced consistent improvement in inequality between consecutive periods, while Zambia was the only country to show a clear increase in inequality (Booyesen et al., 2007).

4.1 South Africa

Cartoon 8: 300 years of oppression ...

Source: © Zapiro; Brower, Liz, 2021

In order to understand the pervasive and resilient nature of inequality in [South Africa](#), it is necessary to examine the country's economic history (Brower, Liz, 2021). To extract diamonds or gold from the earth, labour is required. To make a lot of money from this extraction, you need cheap labour. Cheap labour has been the backbone of the South African economy for hundreds of years; in fact, it dates back even further than the 19th-century discovery of diamonds and gold, to the 1600s when the [Dutch East India Company](#) (VOC) established a trading base in [Cape Town](#). Cape Town was the perfect halfway stop for ships travelling from Europe to India. The VOC's workers needed food, so a proportion of their merchant staff was soon tasked with taking to the soil and starting to farm. These newly created farmers needed increasing amounts of labour to tend to the land and tried to entice the [Khoisan people](#), the original inhabitants of the Western Cape, to work on their farms. However, the Khoisan refused, so the VOC begged the trading company to bring them slaves. Ultimately, the VOC agreed, and [slaves](#) were shipped in from Southeast Asia and parts of Africa. Thus began the legacy of cheap labour in the South African economy, dating back to 1652 (Brower, Liz, 2021).

In 1867, the discovery of [diamonds](#) changed the course of South African history forever (Brower, 2021). By the 1870s and 1880s, the [Kimberley mines](#) were producing around 95 % of the world's diamonds. Following closely behind the diamond rush, [gold](#) was discovered in 1884. By the 20th century, South Africa had become the world's largest gold producer, accounting for 78% of global production at its peak in 1970. The [De Beers Diamond Company](#) was founded by [Cecil Rhodes](#) in 1888, marking the beginning of European monopolisation of the mines. African men soon became part of the mining production cycle, and a [racial hierarchy](#) permeated the mining workforce. The [Chamber of Mines](#), the institute governing mine workers, gave black workers (who formed around 85% of the workforce) short-term contracts and reserved stable, higher-paid jobs for white workers. The Chamber also discouraged black workers from bringing their families to live nearby. For 80 years, the South African Chamber of Mines and its members did not increase wages for their black mining workers! Both [colonialism](#) and [apartheid](#) created an economic system that kept black wages artificially low. By 1971, the average annual wage for white workers was \$5,678, compared to just \$270 for black workers (Brower, 2021).

[Spatial inequality](#) was introduced where location matters most (Brower, 2021). Specific locations were reserved for workers of different races. Labour was brought in from all over

Southern Africa and provided with poor-quality temporary housing. White workers could buy land anywhere, but black and coloured workers could only live in designated areas. In 1898, for instance, there was just one woman for every 98 men. This separation of families had a dire impact on social cohesion. Throughout South Africa's colonial and apartheid history, land laws were used to enforce racial segregation. The series of land acts collectively set aside more than 80% of the land for the white minority, creating 'native homelands' and separate facilities for whites and blacks, as well as a segregated education system. Even 27 years after the end of apartheid, South Africa's spatial inequality along racial lines remains largely unchanged. Black Africans live in cramped 'townships' on average, compared to the leafy green suburbs of white communities. But why does a spatially segregated city matter? Poorer areas, i.e. black townships, have less access to utilities, resulting in more frequent power outages, less water and internet access, and higher crime rates, including a greater risk of sexual assault (Brower, Liz, 2021).

There is a negative and significant relation between the municipal poverty levels and local levels of education and economic activity (GDP per capita) (David et al. (2018). There is also a significant and positive relationship between municipal poverty levels and local inequality levels, suggesting that municipalities with higher levels of inequality also have higher incidences of poverty. In contrast, natural geographic factors such as rainfall and temperature are not significantly related to municipal poverty (David et al. (2018).

Inequality seems to be a persistent issue. The inequality trap is similar. This is a situation in which high levels of inequality remain unchanged over time due to perpetuating feedback loops. This results in South Africa's economy being stuck in an equilibrium of extremely high inequality. The economy repeatedly favours the rich over the poor in such a way that the poor cannot catch up. Inequality traps can operate through a number of systems simultaneously, reinforcing each other, whether economic, social or political (Brower, 2021).

Graph 6: The inequality trap in education in South Africa

Source: © Brower, Liz, 2021

South Africa is a paradox. On the one hand, it is one of the most unequal countries in the world (Francis & Webster, 2019). Half of all South Africans continue to live in poverty, economic growth has stagnated, inflation remains high and the unemployment rate continues to climb towards 30%. However, it also has one of the most progressive constitutions in the world, with a bill of rights that prioritises expanded social and economic rights. However, South Africa's failure to meaningfully address high levels of inequality stems from

insufficient attention to how power, notably social and market power, perpetuates inequality (Francis & Webster, 2019).

In South Africa, living standards are closely correlated with race (Woolard, 2002). Although poverty is not confined to any one racial group, it is concentrated among black people. In 2000, of the country's 44 million inhabitants, around 8 million were living on less than the international poverty line of one dollar per day, and 18 million were surviving on less than two dollars per day. 37% of households survived on less than 1000 Rands per month (in 2002); 60% of the poor received no social assistance; and health expenditure accounts for 7% of GNP, but less than half of this is public spending. The poor are not exclusively concerned with having adequate incomes and consuming basic goods and services. Other goals, such as achieving security, independence, and self-respect, may be just as important as having the means to buy basic goods and services. Since household surveys principally collect information at the household level, they cannot tell us much about inequalities in resource allocation within households. When we talk about poor women, for example, we are talking about those who live in poor households. In reality, many women living in non-poor households may still be considered poor due to inequalities in intra-household resource allocation. However, what does emerge clearly from South African household surveys is that households headed by women are more likely to be poor (Woolard, 2002).

Graph 7: Provincial poverty rate, South Africa

Source: © Woolard, 2002

Graph 8: Poverty rates by average educational attainment of adult household members, SA

Source: © Woolard, 2002

Graph 9: Sources of income among poor and non-poor households, SA³

Source: © Woolard, 2002

Historically, poverty and inequality were forged by forms of racial subordination and discrimination shaped successively by slavery, by colonial settlement and conquest, and by a mining-based industrial revolution in the last quarter of the 19th century (Bundy, 2020). The explosive growth of [capitalism](#) and [urbanization](#) in a colonial context shaped a set of institutions and social relations—the “native reserves”, migrant labour, pass laws, job reservation, urban segregation, and the like—which reached their most stringent form under [apartheid](#) legislation, from 1948 on. The political, social, and economic system of apartheid entrenched white wealth and privilege and intensified the poverty of black South Africans, particularly in rural areas. A historic transition during the late apartheid years saw a shift from labour shortages to a labour surplus, generating structural unemployment on a massive scale. This was a problem that the African National Congress ([ANC](#)), in power since 1994, has been unable to solve and which has been a major factor in the levels of poverty and inequality during the democratic era (Bundy, 2020). Yet since 1994, inequality has increased. South Africa has become a more unequal society and not a more equal one. Two factors have caused inequality to deepen: increasingly concentrated income and wealth, and a sharp rise of inequality within the African population. The ANC continues to commit itself to “pro-poor” policies; yet its ability to reduce poverty, and especially to achieve greater equality, appears to be substantially compromised by its failure to reverse or reform the structure, characteristics, and growth path of the economy (Bundy, 2020).

³ Source: Woolard’s calculations on 1995 IES, Statistics South Africa.

Graph 10: Distribution of poverty levels according to regions in Nigeria (%)

Geo-Political Zones	North East	North West	North Central	South West	South South	South East
Poverty Incidence (%)	77.2	70.1	64.3	60.9	58.2	53.6

Source: CBN, 2013.

Source: © Metu & Kalu, 2020

The six different geopolitical zones in Nigeria have different cultures, economic backgrounds and religions that can affect their poverty levels. Graph 10 shows that the poverty rate was highest in the North East and North West zones, at 77.2% and 70% respectively. This was higher than in the South South and South East zones, where the poverty rate was 58% and 53.6% of the population respectively. The northern region has the highest incidence of poverty, while the zone with the lowest incidence is the south-east, which is mostly occupied by the [Igbo](#) people. The high incidence of poverty in the north can be attributed to culture and tradition, which encourage early marriage and view Western education as a distraction. Similarly, the low incidence of poverty in the South East could be attributed to the Igbo people's internal mechanisms that enable them to seek self-sufficiency, and to the lack of a culture that limits economic participation by gender. Poverty has a rural-urban dimension and can also be identified among different sectors, age groups, levels of education, and genders (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Graph 11: Distribution of poverty levels among groups in Nigeria (2009)

Key Indicators	International Poverty Line (%)		Relative Group (%)	
	Poor	Non-Poor	Bottom 40	Top 60
Urban population	38	62	25	75
Rural population	62	38	49	51
Males	54	46	40	60
Females	53	47	40	60
0 to 14 years old	62	38	47	53
15 to 64 years old	49	51	36	64
65 years and older	37	63	25	75
No education (age 16 and older)	62	38	48	52
Primary education (age 16 and older)	48	52	35	65
Sec. education (age 16 and older)	47	53	33	67
Tertiary education (age 16 and above)	31	69	19	81

Source: NBS, (2018).

Source: © Metu & Kalu, 2020

Poverty rates are consistently higher in rural areas than in urban areas. Graph 11 shows that the majority of the poor (62%) live in rural areas. The percentage of the Nigerian population living in rural areas has continued to increase over the years. The decrease in the proportion of non-poor people in Nigeria over the years is disturbing, especially given the numerous

poverty reduction programmes introduced by different administrations in the country. It is not surprising, however, that the corresponding percentage of the population without an education who are poor has remained the same over the same period (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

[Inequality](#) in Nigeria worsened between 2004 and 2013, but improved by 2016. The Gini coefficient, a measure of inequality, worsened from 0.356 in 2004 to 0.41 in 2013, but improved to 0.391 in 2016. In 2004, the poorest 10% of the population consumed 2.56% of goods and services, while the richest 10% consumed 26.59% (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Accordingly, the lower class accounted for 11.35% of national income/expenditure in 2016, which was lower than the 11.43% recorded in 2013. Meanwhile, the middle class accounted for 30.26% of national income/expenditure in 2016, up from 29.14% in 2013. Conversely, the upper class was responsible for 58.39% of national income/expenditure, down from 59.42% in 2013. Between 2013 and 2016, the middle class saw the biggest increase in income/expenditure shares, while the lower class's share remained constant and the upper class's share decreased (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

There are two main causes of poverty in Nigeria: [market imperfections](#) and [low economic growth](#). The former involves institutional distortions that prevent equal access to productive resources, and includes inequitable income distribution, ignorance, and cultural factors. Low economic growth is associated with underemployment and unemployment, meaning those affected may not have enough income to maintain an adequate standard of living. Poverty in Nigeria can be attributed to many factors, including corruption, poor governance, debt, globalisation, overdependence on the oil sector as the main source of revenue, low productivity, political instability, and poor policy implementation (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Many of the poverty alleviation programmes put in place during the post-independence period had a positive effect on reducing poverty. Such programmes and projects included: The farm settlement scheme of the 1960s, which aimed to develop export and cash crops, eventually collapsed in 1972. Another was the National Accelerated Food Production Project, which aimed to create opportunities to test and adapt agricultural research findings. The Agricultural Development Project (ADP), which was partly financed by the World Bank, was adopted in 1973 to provide credit facilities for agricultural projects and promote integrated rural development, but it soon became ineffective. In 1976, [Operation Feed the Nation](#) was created to encourage self-sufficiency in food and cash crop cultivation (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

While the project succeeded in inspiring a passion for farming, it did not increase agricultural production. The Rural Banking Scheme, established in 1977, aimed to make banking more accessible by providing credit facilities to local people. Austerity measures were also introduced during this period to encourage local producers and reduce poverty by promoting the consumption of goods produced in Nigeria. However, the measures were relaxed by 1979, as they had increased poverty levels in the country rather than reducing them. In 1980, the government introduced the [Green Revolution](#) Programme through the establishment of the [River Basin Development Authorities](#) (RBDA), the Rural Electrification Scheme (RES), free and compulsory primary education, and a low-cost housing scheme. While these programmes helped to boost the performance of the agricultural sector during their implementation, they were not sustainable. Many failed due to poor policy implementation, a lack of political will, and a diversion from the original focus. For example, the Rural Banking and Agricultural Credit Guarantee Schemes failed to provide rural farmers with the desired credit because the mobilised savings were diverted to other investments (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Other projects during this period, such as the National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA) and the Strategic Grain Reserves Programme (SGRP), had a positive impact on the agricultural sector. Similarly, the Primary Health Care Scheme and the Guinea Worm Eradication Programme were key projects in the health, education and housing sectors. However, the Primary Health Care Programme was marred by inadequate funding, a lack of trained personnel and insufficient equipment. The National Housing Policy aimed to provide housing for people through funding from the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria, with the Federal Housing Authority and various state governments involved in the direct construction of housing units. Despite these efforts, many people still lacked decent accommodation. Most poverty reduction programmes in Nigeria failed due to [corruption](#), a lack of focus, programme duplication, and political instability leading to inconsistencies and poor policy implementation (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

During the [Structural Adjustment Programme](#) (SAP) period (1986–1998), the economic crisis that hit Nigeria in the early 1980s worsened the quality of life for many, especially the poor, who were more vulnerable. This led to the introduction of the SAP in line with the modalities of the [IMF](#) and [World Bank](#). The government adopted SAP in order to restructure the economy by reducing consumption and production patterns, eliminating price distortions, and reducing dependence on crude oil exports. However, rather than improving living conditions, the implementation of SAP worsened the situation (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Programmes introduced during the SAP period to alleviate and eliminate poverty in Nigeria include:

- The establishment of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in 1986, which aimed to provide employment for young people with a focus on developing entrepreneurial skills;
- The Directorate for Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), which focused on rural development through rural water supply, the construction and rehabilitation of feeder roads, and rural electrification.

The Better Life for Rural Women (BLRW) programme, introduced in 1987, aimed to empower rural women through skills acquisition and other development programmes. However, it was later appropriated by the political class, particularly the cronies of governors' wives. The Peoples Bank (PB), introduced in 1989, provided credit facilities to people, especially small business owners. The National Policy on Science and Technology, through the Technology Fund (STF), and the National and Economic Recovery Fund (NERFUND), introduced in 1989, aimed to support science. Community Banking started in 1990 after the collapse of the People's Bank, in response to demand for local banking services. The Family Support Programme (FSP), established in 1994, supports healthcare delivery, children and welfare. The Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), introduced in 1997, was another poverty alleviation programme designed to support cottage industries by granting them credit facilities. However, most of these projects and programmes failed to achieve their goals due to ineffective targeting and inappropriate machinery for the poor (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

During the Democratic Era, which began with the introduction of democracy in 1999, citizens expected the government to prioritise improving welfare. On the international stage, the government joined other African governments to establish the New Partnership for Africa's Development ([NEPAD](#)). The aim was to create a comprehensive, integrated strategic framework for Africa's socio-economic development. At the national level, various poverty reduction programmes were established, including the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) and the National Poverty Eradication Council (NAPEC), which was set

up to complement NAPEP and coordinate the poverty-related activities of all ministries, parastatals, and agencies in Nigeria. Poverty alleviation activities under NAPEP were classified into four categories: the Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES), the Rural Infrastructure Development Scheme (RIDS), the Social Welfare Service Scheme (SOWES), and the Natural Resources Development and Conservation Scheme (NRDCS). Other programmes introduced during this period include: The Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF), which is responsible for rehabilitating and providing social amenities such as roads and educational facilities. The Oil and Mineral Producing Areas Development Committee (OMPADEC) was established to provide development for all oil-producing communities, states, and regions (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

In 2001/2002, the [World Bank](#) assisted the Nigerian government in formulating poverty programmes, resulting in the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), which was launched in 2004. The NEEDS strategy covered the period 2003–2007 and was implemented in collaboration with state and local governments in Nigeria. Another initiative was the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (2011–2015), which aimed to develop rural areas of the country through job creation, public expenditure management and so on. In 2012, the Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P) was designed to mitigate the immediate impact of the removal of fuel subsidies by investing in infrastructure and providing 50,000 jobs through the Graduate Internship Scheme (GIS). In 2016, the Federal Government introduced the National Social Protection Policy to provide social protection to vulnerable citizens. The Agricultural Promotion Policy (2015–2020) is also believed to help the country achieve food security, reduce food imports and earn foreign currency through agricultural exports. These strategies, along with others not mentioned, were adopted by various Nigerian governments to address the issue of poverty in the country. The government has also tried to reduce poverty by increasing salaries and wages; however, inflationary trends often accompany such increases, preventing salary earners from living above the poverty line (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Despite all the efforts put in place towards reducing the incidence of poverty in Nigeria, evidences show that the proportion of the population living below the poverty line continues to increase. Most of the youths are unemployed, some are underemployed while some are unemployable. A lot of factors contributed to the failure of the government alleviation programmes and these factors including the lack of focus and continuity, inappropriate project design, corruption, duplication of projects, poor monitoring, poor funding and untimely release of funds (Metu & Kalu, 2020).

Income inequality significantly contributed to the rising poverty in Nigeria, increasing poverty by 75% (Ibrahim & Taiga (2021). Similarly, unemployment and the rising inflation exacerbated the poverty situation in the country. Conversely, growth in per capita income dampened the negative effect of poverty. Inequality is thus the main cause of the weak poverty-alleviation elasticity of growth (Ibrahim & Taiga (2021).

Also, the impact of [remittance](#) on poverty was significant. Households that receive remittances are less likely to be poor. Inequality analysis suggests that inequality is more with remittance receiving households than remittance non-receiving households (Chukwuone et al. (2007).

The GDP growth rate impacts positively on per capita income (inequality), but negatively on poverty headcount ratio. As the economy grows, the gap between the rich and the poor widens even though there is a slight improvement in the number of people moving to a level above USD 1.25 per day (Kolawole et al. (2015).

There is a significant negative relationship between [political corruption](#) and income inequality. However, there is an insignificant direct relationship between corruption and the number of people living in poverty. Similarly, there is a significant positive relationship between corruption and the exchange rate. Additionally, there is unidirectional causality running from political corruption to income inequality. In short, it can be concluded that political corruption is responsible for the increase in the poverty level in Nigeria (Ojo et al., 2020; Onwuka, 2021; Nwosa & Ehinomen, 2020).

The lack of access to essential goods and services for a dignified human existence, the unevenness in the distribution of incomes and fruits of economic growth, as well as constraints in the access to power, self-esteem and freedom coupled with the prevalence of ethnic, religious, gender differences and orientations have generated violence, unrests, war, terrorism and deepen social conflicts, which reinforce the conditions of growing social inequality (Egharevba et al (2016).

A significant proportion of the Nigerian population live below the poverty line. Different Lorenz curves show the distribution of income inequality according to social class (upper, middle, upper-middle and lower) (Lucky & Sam, 2018).

Graph 12: Poverty rate - Lorenz curve for Nigeria showing income distribution according to class (upper, middle, upper middle, and lower classes)

Source: © Lucky & Sam, 2018

Graph 13: Nigeria: Gini inequality index

Source: © World Bank; [The Global Economy.com](#), 2018

Graph 14: Poverty trend in Nigeria, 1985-2022

Source: © ISPI, 2022

Cartoon 11: Poverty is killing us slowly

Source: © Awosiyan Segun, [africacartoons](http://africacartoons.com), 2 December 2018

4.3 DR Congo

Cartoon 12: *balance of rich with rights vs. poor without rights*

Source: © [Brennpunkt Dritte Welt](#), May 2017, No. 298

The [Democratic Republic of Congo](#) (DRC) is located in the heart of Africa and has a population of over 90 million. The country is endowed with an abundance of natural resources which have for decades attracted conflict and war (Mangwanda & Mangwanda, 2025). The peculiarity of inequalities is that countries, regardless of their level of wealth or poverty, can display similar scores (Bungudi, 2022). However, it should be noted that in the DRC, the inequality score remained frozen over an 8-year period, while the GDP growth rate and GDP per capita showed an upward trend. This is because very few individuals and households benefit from economic growth, which has little impact on their standard of living (Bungudi, 2022). The [OECD](#) considers that inequality affects growth through educational attainment and skills development. Economic growth increases faster in countries where income inequality is decreasing than in those where gaps are widening. Education is key: insufficient investment in education by poor households is mainly responsible for the impact of inequality on economic growth (Bungudi, 2022).

Graph 15: *deprivation incidence (mapping by province, DR Congo)*

Source: © Bungudi, 2022

Despite its substantial reserves of cobalt, copper, diamonds, and gold, the DRC has not experienced significant poverty reduction due to its natural resource abundance (Helgath, 2025). In contrast, other countries such as [Norway](#), [Botswana](#) and [Chile](#) have successfully transformed their natural resource wealth into drivers of development by implementing transparent and ethical management practices, rigorous regulatory frameworks and strategic investments in infrastructure and economic diversification (Helgath, 2025). Despite these immense resources, the DRC is classified as one of the world's poorest countries, with its population living in inhumane conditions. More than 71% of Congolese people live on less than one US dollar per day (Shuwa, 2017).

The period from 2005 to 2012 saw a moderate reduction in poverty in the DRC (Kuma, 2020). During this period, the poverty rate decreased by 5.3%, falling from 69.3% in 2005 to around 64% in 2012. However, the number of people living in poverty increased by around 7 million during this time, rising from 38 million to 45 million. Poverty reduction was slightly greater in rural areas (5.6%) than in urban areas (4.1%). In 2012, 77% of the population lived in extreme poverty, earning less than \$1.90 a day. The extreme poverty rate was around 73% in 2018 (the Millennium Development Goals/MDGs target was 40% by 2015), placing the DRC among the sub-Saharan African countries with the highest poverty rates after [Nigeria](#). Extreme poverty is concentrated in the northwest and [Kasai regions](#), and it could increase further with the spread of conflicts to new regions, such as Kasai, and the significant population displacements caused (Kuma, 2020). The poorest provinces are [Kinshasa](#), [South Kivu](#), [Kwilu](#), [Lomami](#), [Haut-Katanga](#) and [North Kivu](#). The DRC is said to be the most affected African country by population movements, with more than 4.5 million people displaced internally, including 1.7 million in 2017. Food and nutrition experts estimate that 7.7 million people suffered from food insecurity in 2017, which is a 30% increase compared to 2016. The extent of poverty varies considerably depending on whether one lives in an urban or rural area, as well as according to socio-professional groups (the poorest are self-employed workers and apprentices (77%), followed by manual workers, employees and semi-skilled workers (66%) and management and collaboration managers (more than 40%) (Kuma, 2020).

Consumption poverty fell from 71% to 63% between 2005 and 2012, driven by a decline in rural poverty of nearly ten percentage points to 65%, while urban poverty remained almost unchanged at 60% in 2012 (Nanivazo & Mahrt, 2016). Provinces that experienced reductions in consumption poverty of more than ten percentage points (Bandundu, Bas-Congo, Equateur and Orientale) have a moderate probability of improving welfare. In contrast, provinces that experienced reductions in consumption poverty of more than 20% (Nord-Kivu and Sud-Kivu) have a significant probability of improving welfare (Nanivazo & Mahrt, 2016). [Kasai Occidental](#), [Kasai Oriental](#) and [Maniema](#) were the only provinces to experience an increase in consumption poverty between 2005 and 2012, accompanied by stagnating or declining relative welfare. In contrast, Nord and Sud Kivu exhibited the most encouraging signs of improvement, with reductions in consumption poverty of more than 20%. They are the only provinces to make gains in the percentage of children not experiencing deprivation in every indicator. However, great strides must still be made to reduce severe deprivation in rural areas, where 60 % of the population resides. In addition to low agricultural productivity, the increase in consumption poverty and decline in relative welfare in Kasai Occidental and Kasai Oriental are likely due to the regions' large rural populations and their dependence on the informal mining sector, particularly diamond mining. Local miners earn approximately US\$1 per day, which is less than the minimum wage in the private sector (Nanivazo & Mahrt, 2016).

The agricultural sector is a source of inequality, providing farmers with different income sources and influencing the determinants of inequality within rural households (Neema Ciza, 2021). The greatest determinants of inequality within groups and households are income level and the area farmed. In the province of [South Kivu](#), for example, the use of agricultural inputs and access to the market are secondary sources of inequality for agricultural households. In the province of South Kivu, the use of agricultural inputs and access to the market are the secondary causes of inequality in agricultural households (Neema Ciza, 2021).

Graph 16: *Gini coefficient and Lorenz curve of global revenue in Kalehe et Kabare, South Kivu*

Source: © Neema Ciza, 2021

Following the Congolese population's approval of the new Constitution in 2006, the DRC began a process of administrative [decentralisation](#) that will divide the current 11 provinces into 26 new ones (Marivoet, 2002). Tracing the geographic profiles of well-being, poverty and inequality revealed that the new provinces of [Haut-Katanga](#), [Mongala](#) and [Bas-Uele](#) will be among the least poor and have the most equal income distribution (with the exception of Haut-Katanga). At the other end of the scale are [South Kivu](#) (one of the provinces most affected by the conflict in the east) and [Sankuru](#) and [Tshuapa](#), which are likely to suffer from their physical isolation in the centre of the country. Remarkable too is Kinshasa's weak position relative to other current and future provinces. Over a substantial range of reasonable poverty lines (282–724 FC), the rural sector is home to the largest proportion of the poorest people. Interestingly, smaller DRC cities with fewer than 100,000 inhabitants are generally less poor than the largest cities, whose FGT(1) and FGT(2) values are closer to those calculated for the rural sector. When we decompose poverty along current and future provincial lines, we see that [South Kivu](#), [Tshuapa](#), and [Sankuru](#) are among the poorest provinces (Marivoet, 2002). While unsatisfactory market integration may explain the poor performance of the latter two provinces, ongoing conflict in eastern Congo naturally explains South Kivu's high level of poverty. Out of the 11 current provinces, [Kinshasa](#) is the third poorest in terms of the poverty headcount and poverty gap index, and the second poorest on the poverty severity index, after South Kivu. As previously mentioned, the capital's very high cost of living is the result of a combination of high dependency on food imports and population demand (i.e. a population of more than 7 million). At the other end of the income spectrum are not only [Haut-Katanga](#), as expected, but also [Mongala](#) and [Bas-Uele](#). Mongala benefits from its position along the Congo River, and these two provinces are also amongst the most equal, which might explain their lower poverty rates (Marivoet, 2002).

Income disparities exist also between provinces, sectors (formal vs. informal), and skill groups (skilled vs. unskilled) in the DR Congo (Ibale et al., 2022). There exists a strong "O-ring" inequality patterns, implying that successful development policies involve a combination of coordinated policy actions. While spatial inequalities are mostly determined by technological disparities, a development policy that disregards the [informal sector](#) has anti-redistributive effects. Taken in isolation, policies targeting education, infrastructure, and labour market frictions can increase inequality and poverty, at least along the intensive margin (Ibale et al., 2022). Moreover, education expansion affects income inequality. Recent economic growth in DRC increased the average income of the population but left the poor behind due to lack of industrialisation and redistribution policies. A positive and significant relationship exists between educational inequality and income inequality (Otchia, 2016).

To date, provinces such as [North Kivu](#), [South Kivu](#), [Ituri](#), and [Maniema](#) (situated in the eastern region of the country) continue to be ravaged by instability and unrest as a result of the proliferation of armed groups and the illicit exploitation and demand for natural resources. There is an undeniable link between ongoing conflict and the socioeconomic challenges faced by women in eastern the DRC that result in perpetual poverty, famine and malnutrition, and unemployment. Congolese women, particularly those living in the conflict-torn eastern region of the country, are relegated to 'second-class citizen' status and often disproportionately bear the socioeconomic burdens created by conflicts (Mangwanda & Mangwanda, 2025).

The DRC, despite being endowed with vast natural resources, continues to experience persistent poverty, an economic anomaly known as the [Paradox of Plenty](#) (Nahabwe & Rwamparagi, 2025). Growth remains insufficient to drive meaningful poverty reduction. Without strategic interventions to improve governance, enhance economic diversification, and ensure equitable resource distribution, the DRC risks remaining locked in a cycle of poverty despite its immense natural endowments. Approximately 68% of past poverty levels persist over time, while 83% of poverty shocks propagate through short-term fluctuations. Projections from 2024 to 2043 indicate a gradual yet modest improvement, with GDP per capita rising from \$1,695 in 2024 to \$1,909 by 2043 (Nahabwe & Rwamparagi, 2025).

The trend in [horizontal inequality](#) is similar to the trend in vertical inequality (Kanyama, 2017). Horizontal inequality in years of formal education is higher among geographical, gender and linguistic groups, and lower among religious and ethnic groups. Horizontal inequality between genders is higher among individuals aged 25 years and over compared with individuals aged 15 years and over. Gender-based horizontal inequality in years of education is also higher in conflict-affected zones (Kanyama, 2017).

However, poverty remains pervasive with a level still among the highest in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), and DRC will likely not achieve any of the [Millennium Development Goals](#) (MDGs) by 2015 (Kanyama, 2017). Poverty reduction has been uneven across regions and inequality has risen (Faso, 2022). Progress in poverty reduction was uneven across regions. From 2005 to 2012, poverty increased in the two Kasai provinces (+35.2 percent in Kasai Occidental and +25.4 percent in Kasai Oriental), while declining in the conflict-torn provinces of North and South Kivu that benefited from significant dividends of stabilization. In the mineral-rich Katanga province, despite an intensification of mineral activities, poverty receded by only 4.2 %. Overall, poverty rates range from 36.8 % of the population in the province of Kinshasa to above 70 % in four provinces (Kasai Occidental, Kasai Oriental, Equateur, and Bandundu) (Kanyama, 2017).

Graph 17: DR Congo : Indicators of poverty

Poverty incidence, measured by the standard \$1.25 a day, is among the highest...

...even though progress was made on both measures of poverty between 2005 and 2012.

Sources: World Development Indicators; Congolese authorities; and IMF staff estimates.

Source: © Faso, 2022

Graph 18: Poverty growth rate 2005–2012, DR Congo provinces

Source: Congolese authorities

Source: © Faso, 2022

5. Conclusion

Cartoon 13: *Inequality and water poverty - Long distance water carrying in Africa*

Source: © Sepponet, Seppo Leinonen, environmental cartoons, 2025

While Sub-Saharan Africa ([SSA](#)) has experienced significant economic growth in the 21st century, its pace of poverty reduction remains incongruently slow. This article argues that high and persistent inequality is not merely a symptom of poverty but a fundamental cause, creating a self-reinforcing "inequality trap" that stifles escape. By examining the interplay between economic, political, and human capital dimensions, this article contends that inequality constrains broad-based growth, undermines institutions, and limits intergenerational mobility. Breaking this trap requires moving beyond growth-centric policies to explicitly target the structural drivers of disparity.

The narrative of "Africa Rising" has been tempered by the stubborn persistence of widespread poverty. Despite periods of robust Gross Domestic Product (GDP) expansion, the region remains home to a disproportionate share of the global extreme poor. Conventional models suggest growth should lift all boats; yet in SSA, the tide seems to lift only the yachts. This article posits that extreme inequality acts as a critical trap, hindering the transformative development necessary for sustainable poverty eradication.

The inequality trap in SSA is not monolithic but a complex, reinforcing system operating across multiple domains.

1. Economic Inequality and Concentrated Capital: High income and wealth inequality (as measured by Gini coefficients often exceeding 0.45) ensure that the fruits of growth are captured by a narrow elite. This concentration has two primary effects:

- * Low Aggregate Demand: The marginal propensity to consume is higher among the poor. When wealth is concentrated, a significant portion of national income is saved or invested in assets outside the productive domestic economy (e.g., real estate, offshore accounts), rather than being spent on local goods and services. This constrains the growth of local enterprises and job creation.

- * Skewed Investment: The elite's demand often focuses on luxury imports and non-tradable services, directing investment away from productive sectors like agriculture and manufacturing that have higher employment and productivity multipliers for the broader population (World Bank, 2016).

2. **Political Inequality and Institutional Capture:** Economic power readily translates into political influence. Elites can shape policy, legislation, and resource allocation to protect their own interests—a phenomenon known as "[elite capture](#)." This manifests in:
 - * **Regressive Fiscal Policy:** Weak and inefficient tax systems often place a disproportionate burden on consumption and labour rather than capital and wealth, limiting the state's capacity to fund pro-poor investments.
 - * **Resource Misallocation:** Public spending can be directed towards projects that benefit connected firms (e.g., opaque infrastructure contracts) rather than universal public goods like primary healthcare, rural education, and social safety nets.
3. **Human Capital Inequality and Intergenerational Transmission:** Perhaps the most pernicious element of the trap is its self-replicating nature across generations. Inequality in access to quality education, healthcare, and nutrition creates starkly divergent life chances.
 - * **Education:** Children from poor households face immense barriers to quality education due to direct and indirect costs, often resulting in their entry into low-skill labour markets. This creates a vicious cycle where a lack of education begets poverty, which in turn begets a lack of education for the next generation (UNESCO, 2020).
 - * **Health:** Malnutrition and poor health in childhood impair cognitive and physical development, reducing future productivity and earning potential. This not only harms the individual but also constrains the overall quality of the human capital stock available to the economy.

The evidence suggests that SSA's struggle with poverty is intrinsically linked to its high levels of inequality. Viewing inequality as a core developmental bottleneck, rather than a secondary concern, is essential for effective policy.

Escaping the inequality trap requires a deliberate, multi-pronged strategy focused on:

- * **Pro-Poor Fiscal Policy:** Strengthening tax administration to progressively mobilize domestic resources and increasing public investment in universal health, education, and social protection.
- * **Breaking Elite Capture:** Promoting transparency, accountability, and civic space to ensure public resources serve the public interest.
- * **Boosting Agricultural Productivity:** Focusing on the rural poor, who constitute the majority of the impoverished, through investment in infrastructure, extension services, and access to markets.

Without such targeted interventions, the inequality trap will continue to undermine growth, perpetuate poverty, and hinder Sub-Saharan Africa's journey towards inclusive and sustainable development.

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Résumé : *[Le piège des inégalités : pourquoi l'Afrique subsaharienne peine à échapper à la pauvreté]*
La question de la pauvreté en Afrique est bien connue et largement étudiée. Environ un tiers des personnes les plus pauvres du monde vivent en Afrique. Les données des dernières années suggèrent que les inégalités pourraient constituer un défi encore plus grand en Afrique que dans d'autres régions en développement. Des niveaux élevés de pauvreté et d'inégalités persistent en Afrique, bien qu'elle soit l'une des régions à la croissance la plus rapide de la dernière décennie. En particulier, six des dix économies ayant connu la croissance la plus rapide au monde entre 2001 et 2010 se trouvaient en Afrique subsaharienne (ASS). Les inégalités initiales réduisent la capacité de la croissance à réduire la pauvreté, et ce d'autant plus si les inégalités augmentent pendant le processus de croissance. Bien que les inégalités de revenus aient diminué de 4,3 % entre 1990 et 2009, l'Afrique reste la deuxième région la plus inégalitaire au monde, après l'Amérique latine et les Caraïbes. Les inégalités non seulement atténuent l'impact de la croissance sur la réduction de la pauvreté et en diminuent le taux, mais elles affaiblissent également la classe moyenne, encouragent la corruption et la recherche de rentes, augmentent la criminalité et la violence, compromettent la stabilité sociale et entravent une croissance soutenue. Les tendances de croissance en Afrique subsaharienne ne diffèrent pas significativement de celles d'autres pays en développement tombés dans le piège de la pauvreté. La combinaison d'une pauvreté endémique, de fortes inégalités et d'une faible croissance constitue un obstacle majeur à la réduction de la pauvreté et au développement socio-économique global dans une grande partie de l'Afrique. Les inégalités multidimensionnelles sont profondément ancrées dans une grande partie de l'Afrique et présentent des dimensions verticales et horizontales qui entravent le développement humain. Les racines des inégalités remontent au passé colonial et ont été renforcées par des institutions qui en limitaient l'accès, établies par les colonisateurs et maintenues par des générations de dirigeants africains depuis lors. Il convient également de prêter attention aux dimensions diachroniques des inégalités, en particulier à leur évolution au cours de la vie des individus et à leur effet sur la mobilité intergénérationnelle. A mesure que des pratiques démocratiques efficaces s'enracinent plus fermement sur le continent, on peut s'attendre à ce que la pression en faveur d'une redistribution sociale générale et inclusive s'intensifie. La protection sociale contribue à réduire la pauvreté et les inégalités en Afrique. De plus, l'augmentation des inégalités de revenus contribue à l'augmentation des émissions de CO₂. De plus, l'augmentation de la pauvreté a un effet néfaste sur la pollution environnementale dans les pays d'Afrique subsaharienne. Plus de la moitié des adultes infectés par le VIH en Afrique sont des femmes, mais la pauvreté et les structures sociales empêchent encore de nombreuses femmes de se protéger. Les stratégies actuelles visant à modifier les comportements liés au VIH continuent d'échouer auprès des femmes et des filles en Afrique.

Zusammenfassung : *[Die Ungleichheitsfalle: Warum Subsahara-Afrika Schwierigkeiten hat, der Armut zu entkommen]* - Das Armutproblem in Afrika ist bekannt und umfassend erforscht. Rund ein Drittel der ärmsten Menschen der Welt lebt in Afrika. Erkenntnisse aus den letzten Jahren deuten darauf hin, dass Ungleichheit in Afrika eine noch größere Herausforderung darstellt als in anderen Entwicklungsregionen. Obwohl Afrika im letzten Jahrzehnt zu den am schnellsten wachsenden Regionen zählte, sind Armut und Ungleichheit in Afrika nach wie vor hoch. Sechs der zehn zwischen 2001 und 2010 am schnellsten wachsenden Volkswirtschaften der Welt lagen in Afrika südlich der Sahara (SSA). Anfängliche Ungleichheit verringert die Fähigkeit des Wachstums, Armut zu reduzieren. Dies gilt umso mehr, wenn die Ungleichheit im Laufe des Wachstumsprozesses zunimmt. Obwohl die Einkommensungleichheit zwischen 1990 und 2009 um 4,3 % gesunken ist, ist Afrika nach Lateinamerika und der Karibik noch immer die Region mit der zweitungleichsten Weltbevölkerung. Ungleichheit dämpft nicht nur die armutsmindernde Wirkung des Wachstums und senkt die Wachstumsrate, sondern höhlt auch die Mittelschicht aus, fördert Korruption und Profitgier, erhöht Kriminalität und Gewalt, untergräbt die soziale Stabilität und verhindert nachhaltiges Wachstum. Die Wachstumstrends in Afrika südlich der Sahara unterscheiden sich nicht wesentlich von denen anderer Entwicklungsländer, die in die Armutsfalle geraten sind. Die Kombination aus endemischer Armut, hoher Ungleichheit und geringem Wachstum ist in weiten Teilen Afrikas ein großes Hindernis für die Armutsbekämpfung und die allgemeine sozioökonomische Entwicklung. Multidimensionale Ungleichheit ist in weiten Teilen Afrikas tief verwurzelt und weist vertikale und horizontale Dimensionen auf, die die menschliche Entwicklung behindern. Die Wurzeln der Ungleichheit liegen in der kolonialen Vergangenheit und wurden durch Institutionen verstärkt, die den Zugang einschränkten und von den Kolonialherren geschaffen und seither von Generationen afrikanischer Führer aufrechterhalten wurden. Auch die diachronen Dimensionen der Ungleichheit sollten beachtet werden, insbesondere wie sich Ungleichheit im Laufe des Lebens verändert und welche Auswirkungen sie auf die Mobilität zwischen den Generationen hat. Mit der zunehmenden Verankerung effektiver demokratischer Praktiken auf dem Kontinent ist zu erwarten, dass der Druck für eine umfassende und inklusive soziale Umverteilung zunehmen wird. Soziale Absicherung trägt zur Verringerung von Armut und Ungleichheit in Afrika bei. Gleichzeitig führt zunehmende Einkommensungleichheit zu einem Anstieg der CO₂-Emissionen. Zudem wirkt sich zunehmende Armut nachteilig auf die Umweltverschmutzung in den Ländern südlich der Sahara aus. Über die Hälfte der HIV-infizierten Erwachsenen in Afrika sind Frauen, doch Armut und soziale Strukturen hindern viele Frauen nach wie vor daran, sich zu schützen. Aktuelle Strategien zur Änderung von HIV-bezogenen Verhaltensweisen scheitern weiterhin bei Frauen und Mädchen in Afrika.